

The Benefits of Teaching English in Multilevel Classes

Abduroziqova Ismigulbegim Inoyat qizi

3 rd year students at Djizzakh branch of The National University of

Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Supervisor: Quvondiqova Dildora

Assistant teacher in the department Foreign Languages at Djizzakh
branch of The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

ANNOTATION

This article discusses teaching English to multilevel courses, including obstacles, benefits, and perspectives on how to conduct multilevel classes. A multi-level classroom is one in which some students know the Roman alphabet and others do not. Finally, the term multi-level can refer to a group of students who collaborate and have a diverse range of talents.

Keywords: multilevel classrooms, diversified, limited resources, assemble, self-access, group work, conversational skills, and various learning backgrounds

The children in multi-level classes are as different as they are. They are often made up of students who talk in English at many levels. They may also be referred to as multi-level classes since they include students with a variety of learning styles, such as those who study primarily from a textbook and those who learn orally. Students' reading skills in their native language may differ.

Teaching Multi-level Classes: Benefits and Challenges

When faced with the challenge of a multi-level classroom, many instructors are unclear where to begin. They are worried about the preparation would take much longer, and the pupils would be more demanding. Schools with multi-level classes may have limited resources, and instructors may be concerned that they will not be appropriately rewarded. Teachers, on the other hand, can only succeed if they evaluate the benefits of a multi-level classroom and apply problem-solving strategies. The following benefits of multi-level classrooms:

- Students can learn at their own speed
- Students learn to work successfully in groups;
- Students develop as self-directed learners.
- Students build strong ties with their peers.
- Students become collaborative learners.
- Multi-level classrooms provide a variety of issues.
- Acquiring appropriate educational materials and resources
- Creating suitable classroom groupings

- Establishing a successful self-access center in the classroom

Identifying Your Students' Needs one of the first things you should do when you're assigned to a multi-level classroom is figure out what each kid need. If at all feasible, this should be completed before the first class. There are several methods for doing a needs assessment, depending on the size of the class and your access to an office and a computer. Many schools provide a standardized test to incoming students. Standardized tests can help teachers determine the language level of pupils in a multi-level class, but they cannot identify the specific needs of individual individuals. In small classes, inviting students into the office for a brief talk might help you figure out what they're thinking.

In small classrooms, inviting students into the office for a quick talk may help you determine their goals (for example, increasing writing skills, obtaining conversational English, and understanding of rules and grammar). Because children may not know the answer, making a list from which they may choose is a good idea.

Give them the choice of choosing between a primary and secondary explanation. Here are some suggestions for a list of alternatives for students to pick from:

-To improve my public speaking skills

- To attend college
- To travel
- To become a future teacher
- To understand grammatical rules
- To please my parents

Many schools, particularly those with small populations of English Language Learners, do not provide separate beginner and intermediate classes. Here are a couple such examples:

- Using the "same" text with small variations for various English levels: There are a remarkable number of a large number of free web sites that give several versions of the same topic at varying degrees of complexity. There are even apps that can do it automatically for you for whatever text you pick!

The Best Places To Get Different "Levels" Of The "Same" Text (This is an external link) has a list of these websites. Students can then be assigned the same tasks, such as taking turns reading it aloud with a partner of equivalent ability and utilizing reading strategies such as visualizing (imagining what the book helps them see) or mnemonics. Implementing a "jigsaw" activity: In a "jigsaw," pupils are given portions of a lengthier text, or, in a more appropriate variant, sections of a multi-level text. class, a modified piece of the same text (see preceding paragraph), or an altogether new text

on the same subject (for example, similarability groups are given bits of a famous person's biography at the appropriate level of text complexity for their group). Then, each group of students with comparable ability reads the book and prepares a poster and a quick oral presentation on what they learned to the entire class.

Creating simple writing tasks using visual cues: I've been displaying six- or eight-panel "comic strips" on the overhead and asking students to write down the story they believe it tells conveys. Students can write it at their current level of English ability, and Intermediates can sit next to Beginners to assist them. There are many of these sorts of image stories available; I used stories from the book Chalk Talks as a starting point and then encouraged students to create their own. As illustrated in the graphic accompanying this essay, they now provide an inexhaustible supply of unique storyboards that students may use for writing and even presentations.

- Differentiating with technology: A trip to the computer lab, or a multilayer class if you're lucky enough to have laptops or tablets for all of your students. Best of the Best Beginner, Intermediate, and Advanced English Language Learner Sites (link is external) has a vast variety of websites that students can use to learn about any topic covered in class (or not).

- Making use of mixed-ability partner groups: This may be a game, a period during which Intermediate students "teach" a scheduled lesson to Beginner groups, a Picture Dictation(link is external) exercise (again, where the Intermediate student is more of a teacher), or something altogether else.

- Providing similar materials for youngsters to work with at varied degrees of difficulty: Among these are the following: Beginners would be expected to practice it exactly as described or with slight changes, while Intermediates would be expected to use it as a model to construct their own.

Cloze (Fill-in-the-gap) of a short text, with the appropriate words given at the foot of the page for Beginners but not for Intermediates. The instructor may utilize clozes that are samples of academic writing that Intermediates do more strategically.

Intermediates would not have another close with the correct words revealed at the bottom, but beginners would. If you teach a multi-level ESL class, you must plan lessons that interest students at all levels. If, on the other hand, student they may lose interest if they perceive the topic is either too basic or too difficult. This is not to say that each class should have three unique lessons. While flexibility is vital for success, you will realize that a well-organized classroom that flows smoothly from one activity to the next is quite possible.

1. Begin by teaching to the middle and then assign assignments at various levels.

Starting the session with everyone together and then breaking off into tiered activities may be effective in multi-level ESL sessions. Melinda Roberts is a nationally recognized telecommunications specialist.

2. Encourage group collaboration.

Group work has the potential to be an excellent tool for students of all levels to learn from one another (Treko 2013). Once I had come to know my students and had a feel of their English proficiency, it was usually advantageous to divide them into tiered groups for certain tasks. Then, whether it was a reading exercise, a book study, or speaking practice, each group was free to pursue its own objectives. To build a sense of community in the classroom, we would reassemble as a class to present each group's work whenever it was feasible and appeared to benefit others in the class.

It is often more helpful to organize students according to their interests rather than their aptitude level.

Overall, teaching multiple courses is difficult yet beneficial to both teaching and learning.

References

1. Roberts, M. (2007). Teaching in the multilevel classroom. New York: Pearson Education. Retrieved July 12, 2016.
2. Treko, N. (2013). The big challenge: Teaching large multi-level classes. Academic journal of interdisciplinary studies, 2(4), 243.

